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AJLOUN COLLEGE STUDENTS' ATTITUDES TOWARDS DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION AND ITS RELATIONSHIP TO ACADEMIC MOTIVATION

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ABSTRACT

This study sought to identify students' attitudes toward digital learning using the Teams application in education, in light of certain variables and their impact on both students' attitudes toward using the Teams and their motivation patterns, as well as the motivation patterns predicting their tendency toward using the Teams app. A descriptive correlational approach was used. The study was conducted on a sample of 500 male and female students from Ajloun University College. A scale for the use of the Teams in learning, prepared by the researchers, and an academic motivation scale were applied. The results showed that the means of students' attitudes toward digital transformation and the use of the Teams were high, and that students exhibited a positive attitude toward it. There were statistically significant differences attributed to the average in weak motivation among low-achieving students, and significant differences attributed to the average in intrinsic motivations in favor of high-achieving students. There were significant differences attributed to gender in the attitude toward using the Teams among males. There were significant differences attributed to specialization in intrinsic motivations in favor of the literary specialization. There were significant differences attributed to the interaction of gender and average in intrinsic motivations in favor of high-achieving males. It was found that only intrinsic motivations significantly predicted students' attitudes toward using the Teams app.

KEYWORDS: Attitudes, Digital Transformation, Teams Application, Academic Motivation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Digital transformation in education has become a fundamental option in light of the steady technological advancements in education and distance learning, especially with the boom in artificial intelligence and interactive learning platforms. Health, epidemiological, and environmental conditions have also played a role in making it a reality at all stages of learning. Ahmed (2008) demonstrated that students' positive attitudes toward digital transformation and its use in education are among the most important factors contributing to its success, especially since attitude as a concept is an important element in educational, psychological, and social studies, in addition to being a product of social education.

Attitudes are characterized by relative stability. People's judgments on topics are often semi-permanent, and therefore can be studied, measured, and used to predict behavior. It is well known that attitudes are learned and acquired, and therefore can be changed, and programs can be developed to support desired attitudes (Khalifa, 2006).

As is well known, there is a strong relationship between attitudes and behavior. This relationship highlights the extent to which individuals think, feel, and behave toward any given issue. Knowledge, values, and especially emotions strongly influence individual behavior. Three factors also constitute the basic determinants of behavior: beliefs, attitudes, norms, and social norms (Abdullah, 1990).

An attitude consists of three components: knowledge, emotions, and behavior. Our knowledge about a particular topic influences our feelings and our willingness to act toward it, which can be positive or negative. Furthermore, any change in knowledge leads to a change in our feelings and, consequently, behavior. Individuals' behavior in different situations can be predicted by understanding their attitudes (Amer et al., 2024; Abu Melhim et al., 2024; Alazzam et al., 2024; Rababah et al., 2025).

Alawneh (2004) indicated that students' attitudes toward digital learning are expected to influence and be influenced by their academic motivation, which is an emotional state within the learner that drives them to engage and participate in the learning situation. Therefore, it is necessary to work to arouse learner motivation because this contributes to maintaining high levels of student performance, especially since learning motivation is a good means of predicting academic behavior that will lead to future success or failure.

Deci and Ryan (1990) emphasized this point,

showing that arousing learner motivation makes their work more effective, their school and classroom interactions more positive, and their enthusiasm for engaging in classroom learning situations and educational activities increases. Furthermore, it makes the student perceive that their success or failure is due to internal factors. This meaning was also emphasized by Santrock (2003), who demonstrated that students who are more successful in life, and who also have a high achievement drive, are more capable of self-control, solving problems on their own, and planning their studies and lives in a better way.

Atkinson and Rotter (cited in Zayed, 2003), explained academic motivation based on expectancy and locus of control theory. They explain that a student's behavior is determined by the expectation of reinforcers and their magnitude, and that expectations depend on the student's self-perception of the likelihood of behavior being reinforced. For example, a student who wishes to study medicine strives to achieve high grades in science subjects, as studying medicine is considered a secondary reinforce (Al-Bdour et al., 2025; Melhim et al., 2023). The student's effort and endeavor in their studies are determined by their expectation that productive work produces reinforcement, and that reinforcement leads to hard work.

Conversely, if a student experiences repeated failure, this leads to an increased belief that success is not commensurate with the effort expended. The cognitive approach assumes that an individual is driven to perform any task by achieving cognitive balance. It is the individual's internal motivation that guides their performance and interaction with various situations and experiences, such as answering a specific question, solving a difficult problem, or making a new discovery (Rababah et al., 2024; Malkawi et al., 2024; Alghazo et al. 2023, 20; Alorani et al., 2025; Almsbhiheen et al., 2023). The individual remains in a state of anxiety until they achieve this and reach cognitive balance. There is undoubtedly a difference between internal motivation, a personal desire to achieve something, and external motivation, which drives an individual to perform a task due to factors external to themselves, such as a financial incentive or a promise. Deci (1996) demonstrated that performance differs when motivation is internal compared to when it is external.

According to self-determination theory, learners differ in their degree of academic motivation, which can be represented on a continuum that begins with weak motivation, then extrinsic (non-essential)

motivation, and ends with intrinsic (essential) motivation (Valerand et al., 1992). Corr and Mathews (2009) classified extrinsic (non-intrinsic) motivation as follows: surface organization motivation, embedded organization motivation, congruent organization motivation, and integrated organization motivation. Deci & Ryan (1990) identified intrinsic or intrinsic motivation as: signaling motivation, achievement motivation, and knowledge motivation.

1.1. Problem Statement

The problem of this research is defined as identifying the attitudes of Ajloun University College students toward digital transformation and its relationship to academic motivation, given the significant trend of various educational institutions toward e-learning.

Clearly, the research problem can be summarized by answering the following questions:

1. What are the attitudes of Ajloun University College students toward the use of the Teams platform as an indicator of digital transformation in education?
2. Are there statistically significant differences in the averages of academic motivation patterns and attitudes toward learning using the Teams platform due to the interaction of gender, academic GPA, and academic specialization among students at Ajloun University College?
3. What is the predictive power of students' motivation patterns and academic GPA regarding their attitudes toward using the Teams platform in education?

1.2. Definition Of Terms

Attitude: Attitude is a state of mental and neurological readiness and preparedness regulated by experience, such that the state of preparedness can direct an individual's responses to stimuli contained in environmental situations (Dweidar, 2000, p. 56). Attitude toward using the Teams platform is operationally defined as students' scores on the Teams platform attitude scale used in the current study.

Motivational Patterns: The term refers to "the set of internal and external conditions that motivate an individual to fulfill their needs and restore balance when they are disturbed. Motivation has three basic functions in behavior: (motivating, activating, and directing it), and maintaining its sustainability until the need is satisfied and balance is restored. The term "motivation" also refers to an internal physiological-psychological state that motivates an individual to

engage in a specific behavior in a specific direction to achieve a specific goal. If this goal is not achieved, the individual feels distress and tension until it is achieved and the desired goal is reached" (Bouhamama et al., 2006).

Procedurally, it is defined as: students' scores on the dimensions of the academic motivational patterns scale used in the current study. Digital Transformation:

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Al-Salahat and Salhat (2023) explored the contribution of digital culture to increasing motivation among University of Jordan students toward distance learning. The study employed a qualitative descriptive survey approach, and the instrument was consistent with each individual. It was administered to a sample of (20) male and female doctoral students. The results of the study revealed that students' digital culture increases their motivation toward the learning process.

Al-Sayed's (2022) study aimed at identifying the views of faculty members at Jordanian universities regarding the reality of digital transformation in Jordanian universities and applying the study tool to faculty members. The results of the study revealed no statistically significant differences in faculty members' assessments of the degree of digital transformation in Jordanian universities based on the variables of experience, academic rank, and specialization. However, statistically significant differences were found regarding the variable of university (public, private) in favor of public universities. The results also revealed that faculty members' assessments of digital transformation in Jordanian universities were moderate.

Mahdi (2021) investigated the attitudes of students at Al-Azhar University towards non-Teams education, and to determine the relationship between the attitude towards education via these sites and the development of self-regulation skills (self-motivation, self-planning, self-assessment, and IT efficiency) among Al-Azhar University students. Two scales were applied to a sample of (605) male and female students, one for the attitude towards education via Teams and the other for self-regulation skills. The results revealed positive attitudes towards the use of Teams in education, and a positive relationship between the attitude towards education via Teams and self-regulation skills among university students.

Kanber et al. (2025) studied the role of digital educational content in eliminating traditional methods in the educational process in Iraqi

universities. the study tool was a questionnaire applied to a sample of 120 male and female students (60 male students and 60 female students) from different Iraqi universities. The results of the study revealed that students acknowledged the effectiveness of digital educational content in increasing student engagement in education and increasing educational outcomes. The study revealed the widespread use of websites in education.

Marq’s (2020) study sought to identify students' attitudes towards using Teams in e-learning at Tanta University. The study sample consisted of 116 male and female students. Three tools were used to collect data: a questionnaire, in-depth interviews, and content analysis. The results of the study revealed that approximately 72% of the sample believed that the best method of education is blended learning between traditional and e-learning. The results also revealed that using Teams increased students' motivation to attend lectures and interact with their teachers.

Hassan et al., (2022) investigated the opinions of students enrolled in the Introduction to Educational Technology course regarding the use of the Microsoft Excellence platform in teaching this course remotely during the Corona pandemic, according to the variables of gender and academic specialization. The study sample consisted of (100) male and female students from the College of Basic Education at Kuwait University. The results of the study revealed that the course students engaged in distance learning in a positive way that contributed to achieving the course objectives to a high degree (79%). The results also revealed the absence of statistically significant differences attributable to gender (male/female), academic specialization, and the interaction between them in learning this course.

Al-Sadhan (2015) investigated the opinions of students and faculty members in the College of

Computer and Information Sciences at Imam Muhammad bin Saud University regarding e-learning using the Blakboard learning environment. The results of the study showed a positive attitude of students and faculty members towards e-learning.

Al-Jabri's (2012) study sought to identify the most widely used electronic applications for distance learning by university students, and the relationship between the level of use and motivation to learn using this technology, as well as its relationship to academic achievement, represented by achievement. A sample of (500) male and female students was selected from Petra Private University. Two measures were developed for the study: the first to investigate the level of use and employment of computer applications and programs, and the second to determine the degree of students' motivation to learn technology through these applications. The study identified the most widely used applications by students, with social networking sites, email, and mobile phones being the most commonly used. The study also concluded that there was a high and complete correlation between the level of use and motivation to learn e-learning. However, there was no correlation between the level of application or motivation and achievement. Gender, academic level, or college were not significant variables in distinguishing motivation.

3. METHODS

Study Community and Sample: The study community consisted of male and female students from Ajloun University College, across all majors, who were studying using the Microsoft Teams application. The sample was taken from the study community and the tools were applied electronically. The sample size was (500) male and female students, as shown in Table (1).

Table 1: Description of the Study Sample.

Categories	Frequency	%
Gender		
Male	96	0.19
Female	404	0.80
Major		
Scientific	119	0.238
Literary	381	0.762
Academic Achievement		
Low	302	0.604
Moderate	100	0.20
High	98	0.196
Total	500	100.0

4. STUDY TOOLS

A. Scale of Attitudes Toward Using the Teams Platform in Learning:

The researchers developed a scale of students' attitudes toward learning using the Teams platform, drawing on theoretical frameworks and some previous attitude scales. The purpose of the scale was to determine the behavioural, emotive, and cognitive aspects of students' views regarding the use of the Teams platform in higher education. Six items made up the scale, which assessed the three aspects of students' attitudes towards learning. Two statements were made in the opposite order. A five-point Curtis scale was used for scale responses. Students' favourable views towards distant learning are indicated by a high score. A score of 18 or above on the scale, which went from 6 to 30, suggests a favourable attitude towards remote learning. Using

exploratory factor analysis and the principal components approach, the validity of the scale's factor structure was confirmed.

Saturation on three or more items with saturation values above 0.3 and factors with a latent root larger than one were allowed. One generic factor indicating the general attitude towards learning with the Teams platform was identified by the factor analysis results. Saturation on all items varied from 0.45 to 0.85, its variance value was 48.8%, and its latent root was 2.93. These findings demonstrate the factorial validity of the measure. Pearson's correlation coefficient between each item's score and the scale's overall score was used to determine the relationship between the items and the total score (see Table 2).

Table 2: Correlation Coefficients Between the Total Score of the Attitude Scale and the Items.

Item Number	1	2	3	4	5	6
Correlation Coefficient	.467**	.825**	.751**	.658**	.639**	.786**

** Significant At The 0.01 Level.

The items' and the total score's confusion coefficients ranged from 0.46 to 0.825, which are high and statistically significant values that show how strongly the items and the overall score are related. The alpha coefficient, which has a reliability value of 0.78, and the Spearman-Brown split-half method, which has a reliability value of 0.75, which is high and suggestive of the scale's stability and appropriateness for use with the sample, were used by the researchers to confirm the scale's reliability.

B. Academic Motivation Scale

Vallerand's (1992) Academic Motivation Scale (AMS) was employed. It was translated and standardised into Arabic by Asfour (2016). A five-point Likert scale is used to answer the measure's twenty-eight prepared items. The three dimensions of the scale's statements – weak motivation, intrinsic motivation, and intrinsic motivation – represent the various forms of academic motivation. Internal construct validity was verified by calculating the relationship of each item to the total score of the

dimension, as an indicator of construct validity. All correlation coefficients were positive and statistically significant. Reliability was calculated using the alpha coefficient, with reliability values ranging from (0.61 to 0.80).

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The first question: "What are the attitudes of Ajloun University College students toward using the Teams platform as an indicator of digital transformation in education?"

To answer the first question, a single-sample t-test was used to calculate the significance of the differences between the theoretical mean and the cut-off point for the attitude scale (grade 18) and the study sample mean. The mean, standard deviation, and percentage weight corresponding to the mean for the attitude scale were obtained. Table (3) T-test for the differences between the theoretical mean and the mean for the attitude scale towards the excellence of the students.

Table 3: T-Test for the Differences Between the Theoretical Mean and the Mean of the Attitude Scale Toward Using Microsoft Teams.

Scale	Mean	Standard Deviation	Theoretical Mean	T Value	Significance
Attitude toward learning using Microsoft Teams	21.1	5.1	18	10.55	0.001

The sample's mean values and the t-test results show statistically significant differences between the theoretical mean and the sample's mean on the attitude scale, in favor of the sample's mean. This indicates a rise in Ajloun University College students' attitudes toward using the platform. This result

demonstrates a positive trend among students toward learning via the Teams platform at Ajloun University College. This result is explained by the availability of the cognitive, affective, and behavioral components of the trend toward digital learning using the Teams platform. This may be due to the

introductory training provided by colleges and universities for students before beginning implementation, through a thorough trial period and the explanation and simplification of usage procedures. The college's use of the Teams platform, which is interactive, accessible, and simplified for interaction, provides interaction mechanisms within the digital learning platform that closely mimic the real-world environment. It also provides the ability to communicate with professors via the platform outside of lecture hours. It also provides asynchronous learning, facilitating students' recapitulation of missed material. This is facilitated by a flexible and accessible online lecture schedule, and the proper training of lecturers on how to use the educational platform effectively, facilitating communication with students.

The COVID-19 pandemic also forced students to engage with and subsequently adapt to the Teams platform at the beginning of the pandemic due to the suspension of face-to-face attendance at schools and universities. This is also due to the fact that the vast majority of students are proficient in using electronic

devices and electronic interaction platforms. This can also be explained by the fact that distance learning facilitates the learning process, reduces physical effort, offers the freedom of flexible attendance, and stimulates students' intrinsic motivation. The results are consistent with the findings of studies by Hassan et al. (2022), Mahdi (2021), Marq (2020), Al-Sadhan (2015), and Al-Jabri (2012).

The second question: "Are there statistically significant differences in the averages of academic motivation patterns and attitudes toward learning using the Teams platform due to the interaction of gender, academic grade point average, and scientific specialization among students at Ajloun University College?"

To answer the second question, a three-way multiple analysis of variance (MANOVA) was used to calculate the interaction effect of gender, specialization, and grade on both attitudes and academic motivations. The researcher verified the significance of the Wilks' Lambda value for the independent variables, and all of them were statistically significant, allowing for the MANOVA test.

Table 4: Multiple Analysis of Variance for the Effect of Gender, Grade, And Type on Attitudes and Motivations.

Source of Variance	Dependent Variables	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	Attitude	655.136	11	59.558	2.453	.006
	Low Motivation	344.956	11	31.360	3.976	.000
	Extrinsic Motivation	1031.977	11	93.816	2.343	.009
Academic Average	Intrinsic Motivation	1099.417	11	99.947	2.696	.003
	Attitude	50.202	2	25.101	1.034	.357
	Low Motivation	122.023	2	61.011	7.736	.001
Gender	Extrinsic Motivation	74.221	2	37.110	.927	.397
	Intrinsic Motivation	287.465	2	143.732	3.877	.022
	Attitude	274.353	1	274.353	11.29	.001
Major	Low Motivation	.014	1	.014	.002	.966
	Extrinsic Motivation	96.637	1	96.637	2.413	.121
	Intrinsic Motivation	30.021	1	30.021	.810	.369
Average * Gender	Attitude	.005	1	.005	.000	.988
	Low Motivation	.177	1	.177	.022	.881
	Extrinsic Motivation	184.920	1	184.920	4.617	.032
Average * Major	Intrinsic Motivation	72.195	1	72.195	1.948	.164
	Attitude	57.133	2	28.567	1.176	.310
	Low Motivation	34.313	2	17.156	2.175	.115
Gender * Major	Extrinsic Motivation	176.798	2	88.399	2.207	.112
	Intrinsic Motivation	541.807	2	270.903	7.308	.001
	Attitude	36.469	2	18.235	.751	.473
Average * Gender * Major	Low Motivation	3.385	2	1.693	.215	.807
	Extrinsic Motivation	73.051	2	36.525	.912	.403
	Intrinsic Motivation	188.825	2	94.412	2.547	.080
Gender * Major	Attitude	4.481	1	4.481	.185	.668
	Low Motivation	1.945	1	1.945	.247	.620
	Extrinsic Motivation	23.440	1	23.440	.585	.445
Average * Gender * Major	Intrinsic Motivation	5.508	1	5.508	.149	.700
	Attitude	17.064	2	8.532	.351	.704
	Low Motivation	157.362	2	78.681	9.976	.000
Gender * Major	Extrinsic Motivation	155.190	2	77.595	1.938	.146
	Intrinsic Motivation	156.695	2	78.347	2.113	.123

Table 4 shows that there were no statistically significant differences attributable to the mean in either the attitude toward using the Teams platform or intrinsic motivations, as the "F" value was not statistically significant. There were statistically

significant differences attributable to the mean in weak motivation, as the "F" value was statistically significant. The results of the post-test differences in the means show that the differences favored low achievers. There were statistically significant

differences attributable to the mean in intrinsic motivations, as the "F" value was statistically significant. The results of the post-test differences in the means show that the differences favored high achievers.

There were no statistically significant differences attributable to gender in either weak motivation, intrinsic motivations, or intrinsic motivations, as the "F" value was not statistically significant. There were statistically significant differences attributable to gender in the attitude toward using the Teams platform, as the "F" value was statistically significant, and the differences favored males compared to females. There were no statistically significant differences due to specialization in both the tendency to use the Teams platform and intrinsic motivations, as the "F" value was not statistically significant.

There were statistically significant differences due to specialization in non-essential motivations, as the "F" value was statistically significant, and the differences were in the literary specialization compared to the scientific specialization. There were statistically significant differences due to the interaction of gender and grade point average in intrinsic motivations, as the "F" value was statistically significant, and the differences were found among males with high academic achievement.

The results show that males are more inclined toward learning via the Teams platform than females. This may be explained by the ease, freedom, and flexibility that digital education offers in choosing a learning location, which suits males more

than females. Females' preferences were lower, however, as they may lose the ability to communicate directly with friends and face-to-face meetings, which are difficult to replace given social and health conditions. This can also be explained by the extent to which males are more proficient in using electronic devices compared to females. The results indicated that those with a literary major were higher in non-essential motivations, such as embedded organization and conformity.

These results reflect a convergence between scientific and literary majors in terms of orientation and intrinsic motivation. The differences were only in non-essential motivations in favor of the literary major. This may be explained by the fact that this motivation is an extrinsic motivation related to short-term external goals. This indicates that students with a literary major focus more on non-essential motivations related to success and assessments compared to those with a scientific major. These results are in line with the results of studies by Mahdi (2021), Marq (2020), Al-Jaberi (2012), and Ahmed (2008).

The third question: What is the predictive ability of students' motivation patterns and academic performance in their attitudes toward using the Teams platform in education?

To answer the third question, multiple regression analysis was used to calculate the significance of the contribution of academic motivation and attitudes toward distance learning to academic procrastination behavior.

Table 5: Regression Analysis Equation for the Contribution of Academic Motivations to Predicting Attitudes Toward Using the Teams Platform.

Predictor Variables	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
Constant	13.065	2.249		5.809	.000
Low Motivation	.011	.101	.007	.111	.912
Extrinsic Motivation	.214	.060	.275	3.553	.000
Intrinsic Motivation	-.010	.061	-.012	-.165	.869
R ² = 0.07	F = 7.4**				

The results in Table (5) indicate the significance of the regression equation, as the value of F for the equation was statistically significant, and it was shown that the predictor variables account for (7%) of the variance in the degrees of attitude towards using the Teams platform. The variable that contributed to the tendency to use the Teams platform was intrinsic motivation. The prediction equation can be written as follows: Academic procrastination = 13.06 + (intrinsic motivations × .214). These results can be explained through the reciprocal relationship between attitudes and motivation. Motivation generates positive attitudes,

and positive attitudes stimulate motivation for behavior. The desire to act and take action requires positive feelings, knowledge, and inclinations toward the goal of this behavior. Atkinson & Rotter explain motivation in light of expectancy and locus of control theory, where they believe that the expectation and value of reinforcers determine behavior. Expectations also depend on the subjective perception of the likelihood of behavioral reinforcement. According to Khalifa (2000), attitudes are valuable because they may forecast behaviour in a variety of circumstances by using an understanding of people's psychological inclinations. As a result,

attitudes have the ability to predict significant psychological occurrences. An individual's behaviour in different situations is predicted by their attitude, which is also directly related to their actions. The degree to which people think, feel, and act in connection to a particular topic is reflected in the high correlation and relationship between attitude and behaviour.

Cognition and emotion have powerful influences on individual behavior. Three types of variables act as primary determinants of behavior: attitudes, beliefs, and social norms. However, the percentages of variation in attitudes toward digital learning based on academic motivations indicate that these motivations account for only 7% of the variance in attitude scores. This suggests the presence of other, unstudied factors underlying positive attitudes toward digital learning using the Teams program, which require further research and study. It was also found that the increase in non-essential motives, which represent the lowest level of academic motivation, is associated with attitudes towards using the Teams program. These motives represent the superficial regulation motive: the individual is driven to obtain reward or avoid punishment, and does not reflect his true desire, and represents a response to external emergencies. The inculcated regulation motive: refers to performing the behavior to avoid feeling pain or obtain the approval of others. The congruent regulation motive: where the student performs the behavior that he feels is important to him and is consistent with his goals and values, which indicates self-affirmation and performing the behavior voluntarily. At the highest level is the integrated regulation motive, which indicates that the student's behavior is integrated within himself with his goals and values. This indicates that the positive trends in using Teams are linked to temporary and superficial motivations and achieving short-term goals, rather than to intrinsic motivations. This may be due to the fact that the use of the Teams platform began with the COVID-19 pandemic and the need to use digital platforms. This type of education also greatly facilitates the learning process, and the motivations associated with positive trends were those that drive short-term and superficial goals for students. The results are consistent with the findings of studies by Marq (2020) and Mahdi (2021).

6. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The results showed a statistically significant difference between academic achievement and academic motivation, with the difference favoring

high-performing students. This indicates that students with high academic achievement are more motivated to succeed academically. Results showed no statistically significant gender-related differences in intrinsic or extrinsic motivation. This indicates that academic motivation is not significantly influenced by gender, suggesting that other factors, such as personal orientation and learning environment, may play a greater role in students' motivation.

The results show that extrinsic motivation is most closely related to students' attitudes toward using the Teams platform for digital learning. In other words, extrinsic motivation, such as obtaining a reward or avoiding a punishment, is the primary motivation for using the platform. The results show that men are more likely to use the Teams platform than women, possibly due to factors such as men's preference for technology and the flexibility that digital education offers, which may be more suited to their needs. The results highlight the importance of focusing on increasing students' intrinsic motivation, such as interest in academic achievement and learning for the sake of learning, rather than focusing solely on rewards or punishments. This will contribute to motivating students to be more engaged in distance learning. This study highlights the importance of increasing the use of digital learning tools such as Teams as an effective way to motivate students, especially in times of digital transformation in education. This requires improving digital education technologies to meet the educational needs of students and transition to interactive learning environments. It is essential for educational institutions to consider the impact of various academic disciplines on student motivation. Curricula should be designed to align with students' interests and needs in their various disciplines, to increase academic motivation and increase engagement with digital learning platforms.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS

Programs should be designed to increase students' intrinsic motivation, encourage students to continue digital learning and motivate them to learn for personal and academic purposes rather than relying on extrinsic rewards. Digital education systems should be continuously developed to support and enhance students' intrinsic motivation, such as increasing interaction and enthusiasm in the digital environment, and ensuring that content is presented in a stimulating and engaging way that contributes to encouraging active participation. Attention should be paid to designing university curricula and distance learning methods to stimulate

students' intrinsic academic motivation by including interactive activities and encouraging critical thinking and active learning. It is recommended that students are involved in preparing lecture content and digital classes. This contributes to their increased

motivation, as they feel they are part of the learning process and contribute to knowledge construction, which makes them more willing to participate in this type of learning.

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